

CERTIFICATE

OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Saidova Feruza Akramovna

**INNOVATION TA'LIMNI AMALGA
OSHIRISH -DAVR TALABI**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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